

Factors Influencing Customer Satisfaction in Indian Banking Sector

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Abstract

Customer Satisfaction is the buzzword used by the business people for the success of organization in the present days. Due to the increases of heavy competition in every product – Line it becomes difficult for the companies to retain the customers for longer time. So retain the Customer for longer time the marketer has to do only one thing i.e. customer satisfaction. In a competitive marketplace where businesses compete for customers, customer satisfaction is seen as a key differentiator and increasingly has become a key element of business strategy. Customer Satisfaction has become a major area of marketing that has received considerable publications from practitioners and scholars in the last two decades. There is a substantial body of empirical literature that establishes the benefits of Customer Satisfaction for firms. It is well established that satisfied customers are key to long-term business success. Higher Customer Satisfaction leads to greater customer loyalty and in turn higher economic returns for firms.

Earlier traditional bank was the only way for making any transactions and it was basically public sector wherein government played a major role by taking into the consideration of profit and social obligations. At present there are several private sectors banks which are established throughout the nation these private sectors are not owned by the government and they are mainly into profit consideration. From the study it is found that certain changes in the functioning of the system will have a great impact on the customer's satisfaction. Before any kind of technology is adopted the customers have to be well informed and educated about it. Customer's satisfaction should be the end goal of any banking sector.

Key words: *Customer, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Satisfaction Models, Customer Service, Market Place*

Introduction

In today's scenario there is a massive development in the banking sector, one of the main reasons being the growth of latest technology. Indian banking industry at the present time has witnessed the roll out of innovative payment transaction and deposits. These banks

concentrate more on customer perspective and adopt the latest technology to reduce the work load. Certain examples are ATM machines; cash deposit machine, Net banking and mobile banking etc.

Customer satisfaction is the measure of how the needs and responses are collaborated and delivered to excel customer expectation. It can only be attained if the customer has an overall good relationship with the supplier. In today's competitive business marketplace, customer satisfaction is an important performance exponent and basic differentiator of business strategies. Hence, the more is customer satisfaction; more is the business and the bonding with customer.

Customer

Different views have been expressed at different times. There is no statutory definition of the term 'customer'. However, the legal decisions on the matter throw some light on the meaning of the term. According to Country Banking Company (1901), customer is a person who has a sort of account, either deposit or current account, or some similar relation with a bank. It implies that any person or a corporate body may become a customer by opening a deposit or current account, or by negotiating an advance on current or loan account. In simple terms, customer is the buyer of the product or service. In the Commissioner of Taxation vs English Scottish and Australian Bank, it was confirmed by Lord Dunedin that "the word customer signifies a relationship in which duration is not the essence". It is now beyond the doubt that neither the number of transactions nor the period is material in deciding whether or not a person is customer. According to Consumer Protection Act (CPA, 1986) the word "consumer" has been defined separately for "goods" and "services". For the purpose of "services", a "consumer" means a person who hires or avails of any service or services for a consideration which has been paid or promised or partly paid and partly promised or under any system of deferred payment. For a banker's standpoint, customer and consumer is the same person who avails of services from the bank. From the bank's point of view, customer is a person who has an account or who avails of other products or service from a bank. He/she is someone who pays for goods or services and customer is one that purchases a commodity or service. However, a person does not become a customer by virtue of the bank performing a casual service like accepting valuables for safe custody or giving change for a currency note. Hence, the dealing must be of a banking nature.

Satisfaction

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2001), satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance (or

outcome) in relation to his or her expectations. It is a function of customer's belief that he/she was treated fairly. Satisfaction is determined by the discrepancy between perceived performance and cognitive standards such as expectations and desires. Wandaogou & Jalulah (2011), states that satisfaction is an outcome or end result during the process of the consumption of a service; it is viewed as post-purchase experience. Parker & Mathews (2001) pointed out that there are two principal interpretations of satisfaction within the literature - satisfaction as a process and satisfaction as an outcome.

The customer satisfaction, only a term which was used in the marketing. It is just a measurement of how the products and the services which was provided by the company to complete the customer's expectations. Customer satisfaction, it defined as the number of customers or percentage of the total customers who reported experience with firm, the product or the service is exceeds specified satisfactions needs. Marketing accountability standard boards given the definitions, purpose and construct of the classes of measures that can come in the marketing as a part of its ongoing common languages in marketing projects.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction plays a critical role in enhancing brand loyalty. It enables companies to retain the existing customer bases as well as to attract new consumer groups from marketplaces. In the current business world, companies need to work meticulously with current and potential customers. They need to be continuously in touch, as customer segment, market necessities and expectations change dynamically. Decision making process in case of industrial customers, as opposed to consumers, involves several people. There are some key decision makers who take the purchase decision. While identifying satisfaction factors of industrial customers, availability of literature is found not as adequate as with consumers. The present study is an attempt to analyze the significance of different factors to influence the satisfaction of customers of various industrial products with their suppliers.

According to Philip kotler, "satisfying is a person's feelings of pressure or disappointment resulting to his or her expectation. Customer is the level of a persons felt state requesting a product performance (out come) relation of the persons expectations.

According to Hansemark and Albisson " satisfaction is an overall customer attitude towards a service provider or an emotional reacion to the difference between what they receive, regarding and what they receive, goal or desire.

According Hoyer and Macinnis said that customer satisfaction can be associated with feelings of acceptance happiness, relief excitement and delight. Since completing his master'' degree in 1988 kavin cacioippo has been for the lending integrated enclosure manufacture. In

his present role as global account leader, he has applied both theory and experience to support the world target semiconductor original equipment manufacturer in the used states and abroad. His work continues to identify, in the perfection of the customer.⁷

Customer satisfaction = f (perceived performance, buyer's expectations)

Here, customer satisfaction is a function of perceived performance and expectations. Perceived performance is the consumer's belief about the product or service experience.

Major influence factor of customer satisfaction:

- Performance of the product in the recent past
- Word of mouth, recommendations or testimonials
- Reviews
- What competitors say about the product or service
- What its own marketers promise

Importance of Customer Satisfaction

- **A Loyal Customer is a treasure you should keep and hide from the world:** According to the White House Office of Consumer Affairs, on average, loyal customers are worth up to 10 times as much as their first purchase. Some research says that it is 6-7 times more expensive to acquire a new customer than it is to keep a current one. Banks or mobile providers know it best, so they don't have any problem with going the extra mile for a customer who is not quite satisfied and often offer him something special. Not only it is more expensive but also much more difficult to keep existing and loyal clients (let alone keeping them fully satisfied and happy!) than to gain some new ones. Take this rule into account while organizing your customer service processes and do your best to look after them.
- **They can stop being your clients in a heartbeat:** Is not rocket science, nowadays clients easily switch their love brands. It is often caused by terrible customer service. Clients waiting for ages to get feedback or comment from a brand? Unacceptable! But it still happens. And gaining clients' trust takes up to 12 positive experiences to make up for one unresolved negative experience. "When customers share their story, they're not just sharing pain points. They're actually teaching you how to make your product, service, and business better.

Your customer service organization should be designed to effectively communicate those issues.” :Kristin Smaby, “Being Human is Good Business”. You can’t gain customers’ satisfaction forever, you need to look after them all the time. Try to talk to them, instead of to them. Ask questions, offer constant support, send personalized messages or offers, use dedicated customer satisfaction survey tool or any other technique that will help you communicate with your customers and collect insights. Take care of each and every one of your clients’ needs and you’ll be rewarded with their gratitude and loyalty. It sounds like a good deal, doesn’t it? Brands often take their audience for granted, and they’ve never been so wrong one decision, or lack of it, can result in losing a lot of clients and their respect. That’s why measuring clients’ satisfaction is so important.

- **It’s (all) about the money, too:** It shouldn’t be surprising, but customer satisfaction is also reflected in your revenue. Customers’ opinion and feelings about the brand can affect, in both positive and negative way, the essential metrics such as the number mentions and repeated transactions, and also customer lifetime value or customer churn. Happy customers won’t look at your competitors offers they will happily interact with your brand again, make a purchase and recommend the product further. If you meet all of their requirements and answer their needs while delivering the best quality of your services, they will be fully satisfied. Not to mention your brand will increase sales revenue! Measuring customer satisfaction should become your daily habit – not something you do from time to time and only if you’re about to face crisis management. If you don’t know how to do it right, you can take a look at our guide to measuring customer satisfaction to make things easier.
- **Customer satisfaction is a factor that helps you stand out of the competition:** Kate Zabriskie once said that “Although your customers won’t love you if you give bad service, your competitors will.” and we couldn’t agree more. Your competitive rivals are just waiting for you to make a wrong move. What is more, they can often play the role of an instigator. Being prepared for their provocations is not enough if you don’t know how to deal with the negative backlash. However, if you

provide your customers with amazing customer service, you will gain arguments to convince those uncertain of your services.

- **Great customer experience can take your brand places:** The importance of customer satisfaction should never be neglected. You should consider it especially while planning your marketing and positioning campaigns. Satisfied customers are more likely to share your content across social media. They will also more keenly interact with your posts, leaving some delightful and admirable comments. Later you can use it as the source for case studies and success stories. Being an example of a company that provides a ravishing customer satisfaction? Every brand should aim for it.

Customer Satisfaction Models

The customer satisfaction model is a set of causal equations that look to measure how happy customers are with a company's products, services, or overall performance. The model is a helpful tool for companies to determine the ways to change, improve or upgrade their products and services with the view to make customers happy. A model of customer satisfaction takes into account various factors such as perceived quality, perceived value, and customer expectations in ascertaining customer satisfaction. For a business, it's one of the best tools to measure customer satisfaction level with their brand and take steps to improve that. The Kano Model of Customer Satisfaction The Kano Model was first conceptualized and created by Professor Noriaki Kano in 1984. It was developed as a part of the research into various factors of products or services that satisfy customers. The Kano Model is a framework to identify the most important features in a product and their expected role in boosting the level of satisfaction for users. It also shows the relation between customer satisfaction level and the different attributes of a product or service. The focus of the Kano model is to help teams view products from the user's point of view. By using the Kano Model, it's possible to create products that not only meet customers' needs but also ensure lasting value over time.

Working: The Kano Customer Satisfaction Model brings a rational, structured approach to product development. It also offers a great insight into the product attributes that are supposed to be important to customers. Teams that employ this model pull together a list of potential new product features or attributes with the capability to enhance customer experience. Those attributes are then weighed according to two key criteria: The resources and investment needed to implement them. Their potential to make customers happy. The

product attributes are split into four categories: Threshold Attributes: Customers expect these attributes and therefore they are the “musts” of a product or service. Performance Attributes: These are features that deliver a proportionate increase in customer satisfaction and customer is always willing to pay for a product for its performance attributes. Excitement Attributes: These attributes are generally unexpected by the customers and their presence naturally delights them and ensure high satisfaction. Indifferent Attributes: They have little or no importance to the customer and neither do they impact the decision-making.

Factors affecting customer satisfaction

The customer satisfaction is the important reason for increasing the income for companies. Also, there are a lot of factors can improve customer satisfaction and work to enhance. Customer satisfaction can improve by many factors such as, price quality. Product quality and service quality and marketplace had strong relationship to customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction helps business to grow up. Also, Customer satisfaction is an essential factor for economic.

Fig. 1. Factors that can affect customer satisfaction

- **Product/Service quality**

Quality is one thing customers look for in both services and products. Quality can be defined as the totality of products’/services’ attributes that bears on their capabilities to satisfy implied or stated consumer needs. Quality is also related to the value of a product or a service, which could evoke dissatisfaction or satisfaction among users. Service quality can be referred to as the difference between consumer expectations and perceptions of services. There is many of smart companies make many experiment for the products before they sales which is very important way that help the companies to gain customer confidence. In that

case, customer satisfaction can be determined by obtaining consumer feedbacks regarding a particular product/service.

The concept of product/service quality is challenging to explore because customers tend to perceive quality in different ways. Theories of consumer satisfaction and product quality include discussions of procedures and professional practices intended to enhance the understanding of customer satisfaction and product quality. The production management functionaries ought to put more focus on understanding, measuring and improving material flow as well as production processes to enhance consumers' perception of product quality, hence, their satisfaction. Organizations can produce services and goods in a manner that exceed their customer expectations and flavour or in strict regard to enhanced safety specifications to boost consumer satisfaction and eventually the business' revenue acquisition. As articulated by Müller and Haase (2015), production control is one of the organizational strategies to streamline product quality. That production control regulates/determines schedules coordination besides monitoring and commanding production activities such as material flow in short-term measures with the aim of improving consumer satisfaction while promoting sustainable consumption. One key element of product/service quality is safety. Notably, variations in product/service quality levels make customers diversify their purchasing choices. In many business organizations, it takes resources and time to improve quality. However, regardless of the costs associated with quality improvement, consumers dislike poor quality services/products. Therefore, high quality in products and services is inseparable from benefits related to product/service costs, which do not influence the degree of customer satisfaction associated with service/product safety attributes.

Fig. 2: Some Factors that can affect product quality

- **Price quality**

Customer satisfaction is an important factor for success of businesses organizations. The product/service price and consumer satisfaction have significant impact on sales. As such, it is crucial for organization management to establish suitable price for their product/service. Price quality is important for customer satisfaction. A product/service price may be established basing on incurred costs and the consideration of both anticipated profitability and sale. As elaborated by Esaki (2013), consumer satisfaction can be attained from inherent quality and price of goods/services from the customer needs viewpoint. Esaki explains that consumer needs entail requirement of inherent attributes and of product price. In that case, Esaki suggests that product/service developers ought to specify quality requirements basing on the anticipated costs, and the product/service price from the customer needs viewpoint at the design stage. Mainly, charging a price that the consumers consider to be fair aids in the development of customer loyalty and satisfaction [38]. Price quality is a strong factor that affect the business.

Fig. 3: Some Factors that can affect service quality

Fig.4: Product quality dimensions

- **Market place**

Marketplace and customer satisfaction the competitive nature of marketplaces influences the level of customer satisfaction. The market place that found in a Special place can attract the customer attentions. Flight marketplace is smart idea for attract the attention of customers. In many organizations, marketing managers find consumer satisfaction metrics useful in monitoring and managing their businesses. Specifically, in competitive marketplaces where business enterprises compete for consumers, customer satisfaction is perceived as a critical differentiator and a vital element for enhancing business strategy. In such competitive marketplaces, the management of customer satisfaction is often effective. On the contrary, in less-competitive marketplaces, the tendency of unsatisfied consumers is often high because of market monopolies.

Conclusion

Customer satisfaction is an important factor in business world and it's a reason for business successful. Customer satisfaction can affected by many reasons such as, product quality, price quality and service quality. In fact, Quality is one thing customers look for in both services and products. Quality can be defined as the totality of products/services" attributes that bears on their capabilities to satisfy implied or stated consumer needs. The customers learn about Brand quality by many signals. Such as, Price, intensity. The concept of product/service quality is challenging to explore because customers tend to perceive quality in different ways. Theories of consumer satisfaction and product quality include discussions of procedures and professional practices intended to enhance the understanding of customer satisfaction and product quality. In fact, sometimes Customers coming back to buy from the same shop due to the customer service. Marketplace and customer satisfaction the competitive nature of marketplaces influences the level of customer satisfaction. In many organizations, marketing managers find consumer satisfaction metrics useful in monitoring and managing their businesses.

Customer satisfaction is a parameter for measuring profitability of business; higher satisfaction leads to higher sales of merchandise and services generating higher revenues of the business. Customers intension to maximize their service values through innovative services offered by mobile service providers; the degree of newness has greater impact on valuing customer satisfaction. Reliability of service perceived by one of the key factors in promoting customer satisfaction; depended on the basis of trust of promoting expected needs at a high level of confidence of customer on service providers.

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